

A NOTE ON METHYL β -RESORCYLATE.

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Robinson and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1496) observed that methyl β -resorcyrate crystallised from aqueous methyl alcohol or chloroform with some solvent of crystallisation which was gradually lost on exposure to air or more rapidly on heating and that after drying in *vacuo* at 60-70° it melted at 118-19°. It is now found that the ester obtained from β -resorcylic acid and methyl alcoholic hydrogen chloride or methyl alcoholic sulphuric acid melts at 78-80° when freshly prepared. Crystallisation from aqueous methyl or ethyl alcohol or air-drying during a period of 3 weeks does not affect the m.p. On the other hand crystallisation from chloroform gives a product melting indefinitely between 85° and 110°. Further, when the air-dried material is left overnight in a sulphuric acid desiccator or dried at 80° for 1 hour, it loses about 10% of its weight and is converted into a brittle powder, m.p. 119-20°. This higher melting compound analyses correctly for $C_8H_8O_4$ (methyl resorcyrate). Crystallisation from anhydrous solvents like benzene and chloroform leaves it unchanged, but crystallisation from aqueous methyl alcohol or dilute acetic acid lowers the m.p. The specimen obtained from the former solvent melts at 78-80° and analysis indicates that it is the monohydrate of methyl β -resorcyrate. (Found : C, 51.2 ; H 5.2; loss on drying at 80°, 10.0%. Calc. for $C_8H_8O_4, H_2O$: C, 51.6; H, 5.4; loss on drying, 9.7 per cent).

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